

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF STONE COLUMN USING FLY ASH, LIME AND GROUND GRANULATED BLAST FURNACE SLAG

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Abstract : The main objective of the present study is to quantify the influence of important factors such as Fly ash-lime content, and curing period on the shear strength and stiffness characteristics of Fly ash Cement mix for its effective utilization stone column. Unconfined compression tests (UCS) will be conducted on specimens with different lime content (3%,6%,9%,12%) cured for 7 to 28 days. An optimum mix of fly ash lime will be found for use in stone column. Tests will be performed on the optimum mix. Empirical relationships will be developed to estimate important design parameters such as deviator stress at failure, elastic modulus, and cohesion of the mix, which can be used to determine Fly ash Cement contents to achieve target strength within a given curing period.

Keywords: Soil stabilization, clayey soil, GGBS, lime, strength characteristics

1. Introduction: Due to the depletion of natural resources and environmental issues, good quality natural aggregates are in short supply. However, the disposal of large quantities of waste materials from the steel industry or thermal power plants with minimum pollution is a major challenge. As a result, there is an increasing need to use these waste materials in road and railway track construction. Steel industries and thermal power plants are often located close together for ecological reasons and together produce large quantities of fly ash and lime particles as waste materials. The fly ash can be used as both filler and pozzolanic. Lime chips are obtained by crushing large lime rocks, and fine lime particles are produced as waste material. Lime has more than 50 % CaO content and binder. A great deal of previous research in soft soil improvement has been found to employ the stone column method with their primary focus engaging towards settlement and deformation behaviors. The aim of stone column construction are to improve the soil characteristics, support the structure and infrastructure overlying both in very soft to firm cohesive soils and also loose silty sands having greater than 15% of fine aggregates. Most of the stone columns analyzed in this study are found to utilize normal aggregate as column filler. Column filler materials normally consist of stone aggregates between 20 to 75 mm, gravel and sand are compacted into a vertical hole generally of 0.6 to 1.0 meter in diameter and 15 to 20 meters deep. Crushed stones or gravel for column backfills should be clean, hard, and unweather free from organics, trash or other deleterious materials. Three main criteria are taken into consideration when selecting an efficient backfill material, i.e. availability, suitability, and economy. A mixture of crushed stone and sand might also be used in the proportion of 1:0.2 to 0.5 by volume. When columns are formed with granular fill, their load capacities become highly dependent on the strength of the fill material and the confining stress of the surrounding soil. To create required strength capacity with stone columns, the granular materials consisting of stone or stone sand should be compacted. Generally stone columns constructed using

ramming or vibro-replacement method either by wet process or dry process, depends on the availability of equipment and its application.

Materials: The materials used for this study are Fly ash, Lime GGBS. Fly ash used in this study is collected from the Dirk India (Maha-co-power plant) of Nashik. The collected samples were oven dried at the temperature of 105-110 degree. Similarly, lime procured from the local market was powered, sieved through 45-micron sieve and stored in airtight container for subsequent use. The reaction of GGBS with water leads to production of silicate hydrates (CSH) from its available calcium and silica. Mainly GGBS is very productive at combatting the swell and also increase the strength of the soil. There are some differences in the chemical properties of lime and GGBS. The mixture of these two substances can be more effective when applied as a stabilizing agent than using them separately. Each of them can produce sufficient silica to raise pozzolanic reaction, thereby demanding lower amounts of chemical activators.

Literature Review:

1. A. M. Asma Muhmed (2013) said, An investigation on lime stabilized clayey soil was conducted to see the effects of lime on the strength and microstructure of soil. 5% hydrated lime was mixed with kaolin clay soil, and different laboratory tests like SEM, UCS, Atterberg limits and compaction tests were conducted. An Improve in compaction properties and reduction in the plasticity of kaolin soil indicated after the addition of lime. kaolin soil showed a 23.6% increase in the PL and 26.6% in the liquid limit. An increase from 29.9% to 33.3% in optimum moisture content (OMC) and also showed a 3 % decrease in (PI) and 40kg/m³ in maximum dry density (MDD). Two variables, curing time and water content influenced the amount of developed strength. UCS decrease with an increase in water content and increase in the curing time. Twice increase of strength has been seen in lime-treated kaolin as compare to untreated kaolin soil. SEM micrographs showed a generation of cementitious material in the treated soil.
2. A. J. Alrubaye, M. Hasan, and M. Y. Fattah (2016) , In this research, the impact of lime studied on the compressibility and swelling traits of soil. Different percentages of lime (3,5,7and 9%) added by the Wight of soil. A series of tests like, Atterberg limits, specific gravity, compaction, and consolidation conducted on the soil. Due to the addition of lime, the (LL) and (PL) decreased. Liquid limit reduction observed by 9% addition of lime. The decline in LL is an outcome of transfers among the adsorbed cations of the clay mineral and the free calcium of the lime. Water content rises from 20 to 23% by the addition of 5% lime. Maximum dry density decreased from 1.63Kg/cm³ to 1.585Kg/cm³ with stabilizer content. Specific gravity increased from 2.64 to 2.72 with 5% stabilizer content (lime) and then decreased with more than 5% lime. According to lime soil reaction, the results showed that the optimal percentage of the stabilizer is 3 to 5% and showed that lime could improve the compressibility of kaolin clay soil.
3. M. Al-Mukhtar, S. Khattab, and J. F. Alcover, (2012), the changes in geotechnical characteristics such as UCS, plasticity, swelling pressure, and permeability along with the micro level composition of lime-treated and untreated compacted clay specimens were evaluated in this study. XRD, Thermo gravimetric Analysis and SEM tests were conducted to the soil. Geotechnical properties changed immediately after the lime addition. Moreover, the treated soil lost its cohesiveness quality and

function as a granular substance. The PI and swelling pressure decreased while permeability and UCS increased. Curing time also had a vital role in changing the soil geotechnical properties, as microscopic changes continued with the changes of the slow pozzolanic lime-clay reaction. Scanning Electrode Microscopic test showed morphological variations during treating clayey soil with lime, dense, thicker, but few large bits with interconnected holes. Figure 4 a and b shows The properties of the XRD, all treated and untreated specimens contain poorly made smectite-kaolinite, with some quartz and goethite. The shape and intensity of {hk} links: {02-11}, {13-20} showed partial disorientation of the clay bits. The determinations and observations clearly showed that the reaction of clay- lime improves the destruction of large clay crystals, beginning from the side of particle supported by the combination of CSAH (Ca⁺⁺ of lime and the outputs of clay dissolution).

4. H. Ali and M. Mohamed (2017) , Many laboratory tests were conducted focusing the effects of delay in compaction and temperature on the mechanical, hydraulic and physical properties of lime added clayey soil. Samples held for a period of 0, 3, 6, 12, 24 and 48 h and 20°C, 40°C temperature earlier for compaction, curing time was 28 days for assessing the influences on long- term strength improvement. All prepared specimens had the same moisture content of 40% and dry unit weight of 12.16 KN/m³. The findings showed that as the delaying period surged the dry unit weight declined remarkably at both 20°C, 40°C temperature, moreover, the greater decline was at 40°C temperature. Tremendous reduction (97%) observed in swelling pressure by compacting the soil at zerhour delaying period and issued to cure for 24 hours earlier to test. Mellowing the compaction of the specimen for 24hr at 40°C resulted in an increase in Permeability coefficient by 400%. Unconfined Compressive Strength increased with the delay of compaction. A surge of 234% and 282% of UCS observed after 24hr of mixing at 20°C and 40°C temperature respectively. According to the results of research work, mellowing the compaction process of lime added plastic clay soil should be avoided to protect the cementitious mixtures as it looks to be the main contributor for improving strength and decreasing swelling pressure of clayey soil.

5. D. A. Emarah and S. A. Seleem (2018), this investigation was about lime stabilized soil mixed by seawater. Influences of the seawater on the swelling reaction, consolidation and engineering characteristics of the soil were studied in this paper. Results showed that utilization of seawater leads to a reduction in swelling properties, consolidation and engineering behavior of the soil. The seawater mixture ends to an increase in bearing capacity of the soil. By mixing potable water and seawater (P.I) reduced by 59 % and 67% respectively.

6. L. Yadu and R. K. Tripathi, (2013), The research has been done to see the effects of GBS on the properties of soft soil. Various percentages of GBS (3,6, 9, and 12%) was mixed with soil. Physical and strength performance tests namely, UCS, CBR, PI, free swelling index, and compaction swelling pressure was conducted to the GBS stabilized the soil. Moreover, the result indicated a significant improvement in the physical and strength properties of soft soil. A significant reduction in the swell-shrink properties of soft soil has been seen. OMC decreased while OMD increased when GBS was added to the soil. Based on the strength test results, 9% GBS was the optimum amount and showed maximum strength among the various percentages that were added to the soil. UCS and soaked CBR value increased 28%and 400% respectively by the addition of 9 % GBS .

7. Sharmila.S, (2016) , In this paper, GGBS used for stabilizing the expansive soil. The utilization of waste material (GGBS) as a soil stabilizer in the construction of building and pavement in expansive soil was the goal of this research. Liquid limit and wet sieve analysis of the expansive soil studied in this research. Then a series of tests like, standard Proctor compaction and California bearing ratio have been conducted to find the optimum moisture content and strength of the stabilized soil. As the CBR value increased from 0.9 to 9% the result of this research showed that GGBS could effectively be as a soil stabilizer for pavement and building.
8. J. Dayalan and Dayalan J (2016) this paper, Studied the compressive strength of soil with stabilizer content (Fly ash, GGBS). This study is about the utilization of local fly ash and GGBS in construction in a way to reduce the amount of waste causing environmental pollution. 5,10,15 and 20% fly ash and GGBS used by dry weight of soil for stabilizing the soil. Various tests for evaluating the stabilized soil like specific gravity Atterberg limits, CBR and standard Proctor conducted on the soil. Based on CBR determination the optimal amount of GGBS and fly ash was 20% and 15% respectively. The results showed an increase in maximum dry density and compatibility of soil while the moisture content decreased by the increase of fly ash and GGBS%. Lastly, the result showed that the optimum value for GGBS is 20% and for fly ash is 15%.
9. S. Mandal and J. P. Singh (2016) this investigation was about the usage of waste material like fly ash and GGBS and their effects on the engineering properties of soil plus improving the subgrade construction of roads. The main target was the reduction of waste materials in the open area. After mixing the stabilizer content (fly ash, GGBS) different tests like PL, PI, LL, OMC, MDD, UCS, CBR both soaked and Un- soaked was conducted to the modified soil. The various percentage of fly ash up to 10% and a fixed amount of 10% GGBS was added to soil sample and the result showed an increase in MDD from 1.73 gr/cm³ to 177 gr/cm³ and a decrease of OMC from 16.5% to 15.8% further mixing of fly ash was led to vice versa result. The laboratory results have been shown that the 10% amount of stabilizer content (fly ash, GGBS) increase the amount of soaked and un-soaked from 1.6 Kg/cm² to 4.17Kg/cm² and 2.35Kgr/cm to 4.51 Kgr/cm² respectively. Finally, the recommended value of fly ash and GGBS that should be used in soil denoted a value of about 10%.
10. M. Keramatikerman, A. Chegenizadeh, and H. Nikraz, (2016) this study was about the partial replacement of lime with GGBS. Also, a comparison between lime stabilized soil and GGBS substitution by conducting the (VSS)volumetric shrinkage strain, UCS and (SR)share strength tests. The results of VSS showed that the usage of GGBS with lime led to an effective reduction in volumetric shrinkage. The (UCS) results showed that the partial replacement of lime with GGBS ended with higher compressive strength and share strength (fig 7). Microstructural studies like (SEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) carried out on modified lime stabilized soil shows that the mixture of GGBS in lime-stabilized clay led to the production of cementations material. XRD test showed that calcium silicate hydrates (CSH) are the primary hydration production in the lime.
11. L. C. Dang, B. Fatahi, and H. Khabbaz,(2016) Bagasse fibre and lime added to the expansive nature soil for reinforcing the soil particles. Bagasse fibre is an industrial waste, a residual of sugar cane juice left after extraction. The chosen soil had been collected from Queensland, Australia. The expansive soil had been added by 0.5%,1% and 2% Bagasse fibre and lime for stabilisation purposes.

UCS and linear shrinkage tests undertook for 3,7 and 28-day curing period the paper has shown that linear shrinkage dip while UCS values of treated soil surge with the increase of stabilizer's percentage. This research found that a blend of hydrated lime-bagasse fibre has a better result in case of strength than bagasse fibre alone.

12. M. Al-Mukhtar, A. Lasledj, and J. F. Alcover (2010) The study was about the treatment of highly expansive and very plastic clay soil, pozzolanic reaction progress of clayey soil has been evaluated in 50 C temperature and different curing periods. By conducting different laboratory tests on soil, this has been observed that a large quantity of lime (>5%), is required to defeat with the silicate layer and destroy them to create the various hydrates in the processed soil. Addition of lime above the needed amount (5%) to the treated soil for the cation transfer cause the pozzolanic reaction formation of a new form: CAH and CSH at high temperatures, curing time and high lime content. A significant development in the UCS test is achieved by lime addition. Rising curing temperature from 20° to 50° increased the rate of pozzolanic reaction by 600%.

13. H. Canakci, F. Celik, M. O. A. Bizne, and M. O. A. Bizne, (2016) investigated the effects of waste aluminium beverage can (WBC) pieces on the swelling and strength characteristics of the lean clay soil. An amount of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 % (WBC) mixed with soil. Compaction, CBR and free swelling tests carried out to investigate the effects of the stabilizers on the soil engineering properties. The results showed that the addition of (WBC) leads to an increase in MDD and a decrease in the OMC of the soil. These stirrups are considered as environmentally friendly materials and the effective amount of stabilizer was found as 6%.

14. D. C. Sekhar and S. Nayak, (2018) this research investigated the GGBS and cement stabilized earth blocks (CSEB). Two different types and locally available soil, Dakshina of Kannada district and Karnataka, India was selected for the investigation. First, an optimum amount of GGBS discovered after that different amounts of cement added to the soil for the generation of the size of 305 mm *143 mm *105 mm compacted (CSEBs). After 28 days curing, the results revealed that the GGBS and cement made (CSEBs) can be used as load-bearing walls in buildings. The excellent percentage of GBFS denoted as 25% and 20% for stabilizing the lithomargic clay and lateritic soil. By adding 25% and 20% GGBS, an enhancement of about 53% and 40% in the strength of lithomargic and lateritic made blocks has seen in the results see Fig 10 and 11. An amount of 10% cement along with optimum of GGBS raised the strength of blocks by 390%.

3. Methodology:

- Literature Review - i. Detailed study of research papers and journals
- Collection of materials - i. Collection of fly ash, lime & ground granulated blast furnace slag
- Material Testing - i. Sieve analysis ii. Specific gravity
- Standard Proctor Test - i. For finding out OMC and MDD.
ii. For 10% , 15% , 20% , 25% , 30% water content.
- UCS Test -For finding out unconfined compressive strength. 6 samples of each design mix for 7, 14, 28 days curing for OMC.
- Direct Shear Test- i. To determine cohesion (c) & friction angle (Φ).
- Durability Test – i. To determine durability of soil

- Consistency Limit – To determine resistance of soil against deformation & rupture
- CBR Test- i. To determine Bearing capacity of Soil.
- Laboratory model test i. To determine deflection and load carrying capacity.

3.1 Sieve Analysis: The grain size analysis test is performed to determine the percentage of each size of grain that is contained within a sample, and the results of the test can be used to produce the grain size distribution curve. This information is used to classify the soil and to predict its behavior. ASTM D 6913 Standard Test Methods for Particle-Size Distribution (Gradation) of Soils Using Sieve Analysis. The particle size distribution was determined by using dry sieve method for given sample of bottom ash as per IS: 2720 (Part 4) 1985. Particle size distribution curve of fly ash shows that coefficient of uniformity (C_u) and coefficient of curvature (C_c) for Bottom ash were found to be 12.353 & 1.01 respectively. Thus, sample is well graded.

3.2 Specific Gravity: The specific gravity of fly ash and Bottom ash was determined by Pycnometer method as per IS: 2720 (Part 2) 1964. The specific gravity of the fly ash, Bottom ash and soil used is 2.09, 2.38 and 2.306 respectively. The Pycnometer is chiefly utilized for the determination of the specific gravity of soil particles of both types fine grained and coarse grained soils.

3.3 Standard Proctor Test: Standard proctor method is used to determine the soil compaction properties, specifically, to determine the optimal water content at which soil can reach its maximum dry density. The original test is often referred to as Standard Proctor Test, which was later modified and referred to as Modified Proctor Test. To determine the relationship between moisture content and dry density of soil. This test provides optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD) of a given soil, which is important for man-made construction. The results obtained from this test will be helpful in increasing the bearing capacity of soil, decreasing the undesirable settlements, controlling undesirable volume changes, reducing hydraulic conductivity, increasing the stability of slopes and so on.

3.4 Unconfined Compressive Strength Test: Depending on the mix proportion, required amounts of materials, namely fly ash, lime and GGBS were first mixed in a dry state. The water corresponding to OMC was then added and mixed thoroughly. Next, cylindrical specimens of 50 mm diameter and 100 mm high were compacted by a static press in three layers to achieve dry unit weight equal to the MDD of the mix obtained from Standard Proctor compaction test. Immediately after preparation, the specimens were sealed in airtight polythene bags and kept at a temperature of $27 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for curing. To study the effect of curing period on UCS, the specimens were cured for 7 and 28 days. The values of UCS of the cured specimens were then determined in a conventional compression testing machine at a constant strain rate of 0.6 mm/ min. Because of a typical scatter of UCS data, three identical specimens were tested for each trial mix. As an acceptance criterion, the specimen, whose individual strength deviated by more than 10% from an average strength of the three identical specimens, was rejected. The tests were conducted on all combinations of FLG mixes as previously explained.

3.5 Direct Shear Test: It is used to determine the shear strength of the soil. It is more suitable for cohesionless soils. Using direct shear test, one can find out the cohesion and angle of internal friction of soil which are useful in many engineering designs such as foundations, retaining walls, etc. This test can be performed in three different drainage conditions namely unconsolidated-undrained,

consolidated-undrained and consolidated-drained conditions. In general, cohesionless soils are tested for direct shear in consolidated drained condition. A small normal load for seating is applied after the shear box is placed in the shear device. After proper alignment of the components, apply the main normal load. Then the sample is sheared along the horizontal plane. This indicates that the failure plane is horizontal. The parameters (c and ϕ) of the soil sample depend upon the degree of saturation and density of the particular soil sample.

3.6 California Bearing Ratio Test: The California Bearing Ratio test (CBR test) is a penetration test developed by California State Highway Department for evaluating the strength of subgrade soil, other paved areas and their used materials. CBR testing is used in the design of flexible pavements and since its development, it has been widely adopted internationally. The

California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test is a measure of resistance of a material to penetration of standard plunger under controlled density and moisture conditions. It was developed by the California Division of Highways as a method of classifying and evaluating soil- subgrade and base course materials for flexible pavements. CBR test may be conducted in remoulded or undisturbed sample. Test consists of causing a cylindrical plunger of 50mm diameter to penetrate a pavement component material at 1.25mm/minute. The loads for 2.5mm and 5mm are recorded. This load is expressed as a percentage of standard load value at a respective deformation level to obtain CBR value.

3.7 Triaxial Shear Test: It is used to determine the shear strength of the soil. It is more suitable for cohesionless soils. Using direct shear test, one can find out the cohesion and angle of internal friction of soil which are useful in many engineering designs such as foundations, retaining walls, etc. This test can be performed in three different drainage conditions namely unconsolidated-undrained, consolidated-undrained and consolidated-drained conditions. In general, cohesionless soils are tested for direct shear in consolidated drained condition.

3.8 Durability Test: The durability of the optimum 90F1L9G is assessed in reference to ASTM D559 (ASTM 2015). 90F1L9 was subjected to 12 cycles of alternating wetting and drying. Figure represents the accumulated weight loss after each wet–dry cycle. It can be observed that the loss of weight after 12 wet–dry cycles was 0.6 %, which was less than the 14% limit recommended by IRC 37 (IRC 2012).

4. Results:

4.1 Sieve Analysis: Table 1: Cu and Cc of various materials

Material	coefficient of uniformity (Cu)	coefficient of curvature (Cc)
Bottom Ash	12.353	1.01

Figure 1: Graph between percent Wt. Passing Vs Sieve Size

4.2 Specific Gravity:

Table 2: specific gravity of various materials

Material	Specific Gravity
Fly Ash	2.09
Bottom Ash	2.38
Soil	2.306

Figure 3: Variation of Dry Density Vs Moisture Content

Figure 4: Variation of Dry Density Vs Moisture Content Table 3: percentage water and MDD for various proportion of Lime

2 % lime + 3 % GGBS		2 % lime + 6 % GGBS		2 % lime + 9 % GGBS		2 % lime + 12% GGBS	
% water	MDD	% water	MD D	% water	MDD	% water	MDD
12.5	1.14	12.3	1.26	11.1	1.283	8.3	1.30
16.3	1.25	15.1	1.281	13.8	1.291	12.1	1.315
20.1	1.261	18.7	1.284	17.01	1.314	16.2	1.321
23.4	1.243	20.1	1.268	19.2	1.296	18.9	1.31

Table 4: percentage water and MDD for various proportion of Lime

3 % lime + 3 % GGBS		3 % lime + 6 % GGBS		3 % lime + 9 % GGBS		3 % lime + 12% GGBS	
% water	MDD	% water	MD D	% water	MDD	% water	MDD
17.3	1.279	11.3	1.300	7.6	1.313	2.5	1.342
17.9	1.29	13.1	1.312	9.5	1.32	5.3	1.351
20.0	1.301	17.4	1.302	12.3	1.327	7.5	1.36
24.1	1.285	19.7	1.301	16.9	1.321	10.2	1.351

Figure 5: Variation of Dry Density Vs Moisture Content

4.3 California Bearing Ratio Test:

Table 3: Penetration at different load conditions

Penetration (mm)	Standard Load (Kg)	Unit Standard Load (Kg/cm ²)
2.5	1370	1.635
5.0	2055	1.482

4.4 Unconfined Compressive Strength Test:

Table No 4: Average stress of various samples

Sr No	Sample	Avg .Stress (Mpa)		
		7 days	14 days	28 days
1	1L3G	0.608	1.152	1.458
2	1L6G	1.810	2.599	2.820
3	1L9G	1.706	3.196	4.780
4	2L3G	1.19	1.47	2.500
5	2L6G	3.39	5.50	6.240
6	2L9G	3.70	2.530	2.820

4.5 Test Setup: The stone column was extended to the full depth of the clay placed in the tank for a height of 350 mm so that l/d ratio length of the column/diameter of the column is a minimum of 5, which is required to develop the full limiting axial stress on the column Mitra and Chattopadhyay 1999. Vertical stress was applied either over the entire tank area or only over the stone column. The load was applied through a proving ring at a constant displacement rate of 0.0625 mm/min. A proving ring is a steel ring of approximately 200 diameter, the deformation of which is measured using a mechanical displacement gauge to arrive at the axial load applied through the ring. A sand layer of 30 mm thick was placed at the top to serve as a blanket for the case where the entire area is loaded. Tests were also carried out on a group of seven columns arranged in a triangular pattern where the clay area corresponding to an equivalent area of seven unit cells is represented by the tank. To compare the behavior with a single column and to check the stress distribution between stone column and clay. The load was applied through a 16 mm thick mild steel plate with stiffeners to ensure negligible structural deformation. The locations of pressure cells fixed along the bottom surface of the loading plate.

4.6 Comparison of Laboratory Tests and FEM Analysis

4.6.1 Column Entire Area Loaded: This analysis aims at evaluating the improvement of the stiffness of the treated ground. The loading of both the stone column and the surrounding equivalent area with confinement of the tank wall represents an actual field condition for the interior columns of a large group of stone columns. Typical axial stress versus settlement behavior for improved and unimproved grounds based on model tests as well as finite-element analysis for different shear strengths and for s/d of 2. When the entire area is loaded, because of the confining effect from the

boundary of the unit cell, failure does not take place even for a settlement as high as 10 mm. Typical axial stress versus settlement behavior from model test and finite-element analysis for different s/d and for a shear strength of 30 kPa. As the axial stress versus settlement relation is almost linear, stiffness Young's Modulus of the improved ground

Figure 6: Graph between Displacement Vs Load

5. Conclusion

- With addition of lime maximum dry density increases and optimum moisture content decreases.
- Addition of lime results in filling the voids of the compacted fly ash thus increases the density.
- The optimum moisture content (OMC) was found to decrease while the maximum dry density (MDD) increased with increasing binder content.
- The design mixes 9 % lime, 2% lime 6 % GGBS, 3 % lime 6 % GGBS satisfies the IRC requirement of 1.5MPa field value.
- Mix proportion 2% lime 6% GGBS is nearly 42% cheaper than proportion 9% lime, whereas Mix proportion 3% lime 6% GGBS is nearly 35% cheaper than proportion 9% lime.

References

- [1] A. M. Asma Muhmed, "Effect of Lime Stabilisation on the Strength and Microstructure of Clay," IOSR J. Mech. Civ. Eng., vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 87–94, 2013.
- [2] A. J. Alrubaye, M. Hasan, and M. Y. Fattah, "Engineering properties of clayey soil stabilized with lime," ARPN J. Eng. Appl. Sci., vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 2434–2441, 2016.
- [3] M. Al-Mukhtar, S. Khattab, and J. F. Alcover, "Microstructure and geotechnical properties of lime-treated expansive clayey soil," Eng. Geol., vol. 139–140, pp. 17–27, 2012.
- [4] H. Ali and M. Mohamed, "The effects of compaction delay and environmental temperature on the mechanical and hydraulic properties of lime-stabilized extremely high plastic clays," Appl. Clay Sci., vol. 150, no. September, pp. 333–341, 2017.
- [5] D. A. Emarah and S. A. Seleem, "Swelling soils treatment using lime and sea water for roads construction," Alexandria Eng. J., vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 2357–2365, 2018.

- [6] L. Yadu and R. K. Tripathi, “Effectiveness of Granulated Blast Furnace Slag Over Sand As Overlay for the Stabilization of Soft Clay,” no. 2, pp. 32–37, 2013.
- [7] Sharmila.S, “Stabilization of Expansive soil using Ground Granulated Blast furnace Slag,” *Int. J. Mod. Trends Eng. Res.*, vol. 3, no. 9, pp. 102–106, 2016.
- [8] J. Dayalan and Dayalan J, “Comparative Study On Stabilization of Soil With Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS) and Fly Ash,” *Int. Res. J. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 2198–2204, 2016.
- [9] S. Mandal and J. P. Singh, “Stabilization of Soil using Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag and Fly Ash,” *Ijirset*, vol. 5, no. 12, pp. 21121–21126, 2016.
- [10] M. Keramatikerman, A. Chegenizadeh, and H. Nikraz, “Effect of GGBFS and lime binders on the engineering properties of clay,” *Appl. Clay Sci.*, vol. 132–133, pp. 722–730, 2016.
- [11] L. C. Dang, B. Fatahi, and H. Khabbaz, “Behaviour of Expansive Soils Stabilized with Hydrated Lime and Bagasse Fibres,” *Procedia Eng.*, vol. 143, no. 1, pp. 658–665, 2016.
- [12] M. Al-Mukhtar, A. Lasledj, and J. F. Alcover, “Behaviour and mineralogy changes in lime-treated expansive soil at 20°C,” *Appl. Clay Sci.*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 191–198, 2010.
- [13] H. Canakci, F. Celik, M. O. A. Bizne, and M. O. A. Bizne, “Stabilization of Clay with Using Waste Beverage Can,” *Procedia Eng.*, vol. 161, pp. 595–599, 2016.
- [14] D. C. Sekhar and S. Nayak, “Utilization of granulated blast furnace slag and cement in the manufacture of compressed stabilized earth blocks,” *Constr. Build. Mater.*, vol. 166, pp. 531–536, 2018.